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Three-cycle Engineering Education based on the CDIO-FCDI-FFCD Triad

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Introduction

One of the principle objectives for improving quality of engineering education (EE) of the three-cycle structure formed within the framework of the Bologna process, is to ensure EE compliance with the labor market demands and continuity of the relevant programmes. First, it concerns the definition of programme learning outcomes (LOs). It is necessary to bring them into line with the peculiarities of the division of labor in the engineering profession. Further, it is important to design programmes that ensure the achievement of intended LOs using appropriate content and technologies.

The CDIO model developed at the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries allowed the modernization of the basic EE by establishing a consensus between theory and practice [1]. The CDIO model focuses BEng programme LOs on complex engineering activity of graduates at the following stages of the life cycle of products, processes and systems: “Conceive”, “Design”, “Implement” and “Operate”. The CDIO approach has proved its effectiveness, and many universities around the world successfully applied the approach in practice (<http://cdio.org/>). The CDIO model has become also of great importance for the development of the theory of EE [2].

However, the practice of applying CDIO Standards to the design of MSc and PhD programmes aimed at preparing graduates for research and development of innovative products has shown the need for adaptation of the CDIO Standards to the specifics of research and innovative activities [3]. Thus, it became necessary to further develop the CDIO approach for the modernization of the three-cycle EE, taking into account the various graduate competencies required for successful research, innovative and complex engineering activities.

To clarify the competencies which should be formed on the three cycles of EE, a thorough comparative analysis of the main documents defining international standards of EE was made, including the qualifications requirements: The Framework for Qualifications of the European Higher Education Area (<http://ecahe.eu/w/index.php>), FEANI Register (<https://www.feani.org>); criteria of engineering programme accreditation: EUR-ACE Framework Standards and Guidelines (<http://www.enaee.eu>), IEA Graduate Attributes and Professional Competences (<http://www.ieagrements.org>); basic principles of quality assessment of PhD programmes in European universities: Quality Assurance in Doctoral Education – results of the ARDE project (<https://www.researchgate.net>), as well as LOs of three levels of higher education (bachelor, master, doctor) at universities in Europe, the US and Russia.

The lists of the core competences of graduates of engineering BEng, MSc and PhD programmes have been composed as a result of system analysis of the documents mentioned above and synthesis of the most relevant competences required for complex, innovative and research engineering activity, respectively.

1 The FCDI model for engineering MSc programme design

Based on the core competences of graduates of MSc programme required for innovative engineering activity the FCDI (Forecast, Conceive, Design, Implement) model for the design of engineering MSc programmes was developed [4]. A FCDI programme is based on the principle that innovative product, process, and system lifecycle design and development – Forecasting, Conceiving, Designing and Implementing is an adequate competence model for MSc degree in engineering. The “Forecast” stage includes analyzing the market trends; making predictions of future customer needs; estimating risk and uncertainty; determining the most demanded and competitive innovative products, processes, and systems. The “Conceive” stage includes feasibility study; modelling and simulation; development of advanced technique and technology; assessment of the economic impact of innovations; planning and creation of R&D resources for innovative product, process, or system design. The “Design” stage focuses on designing & developing of innovative product, process, or system taking into consideration severe limitations. The “Implement” stage mainly refers to the production management when implementing innovative projects, as well as controlling of the advanced technology when manufacturing and coding. The absence of “Operate” stage (one of the CDIO components) in the FCDI model indicates that this kind of engineering activity (operation and maintenance of products, processes and systems) is not a priority for MSc programme graduates.

The FCDI Syllabus v1 and FCDI Standards v1 were developed as a result of evolution of the list of LOs presented in the CDIO Syllabus v2 and CDIO Standards, respectively [1]. The FCDI Syllabus v1 focuses the attention of the MSc programme designers on the need to provide Masters with a deeper interdisciplinary scientific and technical

knowledge, and professional competences to forecast customer needs in innovations and to conceive, design and implement new products, processes and systems. The FCDI Standards v1 focus the attention of the MSc programme designers on integrated curriculum with mutually supporting interdisciplinary courses, innovation activity with an explicit plan of integration of personal and interpersonal skills, as well as innovative product, process, and system design and development skills based on forecasting the stakeholders' needs (Standard 3 FCDI). The essential elements of the curriculum should be an introductory workshop that provides the framework for engineering practice in innovative product, process and system design and development based on forecasting the needs of stakeholders (Standard 4 FCDI); innovation-design experiences (Standard 5 FCDI); teaching and learning based on active learning and innovative methods (Standard 8 FCDI).

2 The FFCD model for engineering PhD programme design

Based on the core competences of graduates of PhD programme required for research engineering activity the FFCD (Foresight, Forecast, Conceive, Design) model was developed for the design of engineering PhD programmes [4]. A FFCD programme is based on the principle that creation of scientific basis for the development and design of innovative product, process, and system lifecycle – Foreseeing, Forecasting, Conceiving and Designing is an adequate competence model for PhD degree in engineering. The “Foresight” stage includes future study; long-term vision; analyses of the society needs; research & innovation planning; technological foresight; analyses of “critical” technologies. The “Forecast” stage includes knowledge management; research and new knowledge generation; critical analyses of scientific data; assessment of knowledge-intensive technology needs. The “Conceive” stage includes creation of scientific basis for the development and design of innovative product, process, or system; development of new technique and technology based on up-to-date knowledge. The “Design” stage focuses on scientific support of knowledge-intensive innovative product, process, or system design and development. The absence of “Implement” stage (one of the CDIO components) in the FFCD model indicates that participation in manufacturing of products, processes and systems is not a priority for PhD programme graduates.

The FFCD Syllabus v1 and FFCD Standards v1 were developed as a result of evolution of the list of LOs presented in the FCDI Syllabus v1 and FCDI Standards v1. The FFCD Syllabus v1 focuses the attention of the PhD programme designers on the need for PhD-holders to acquire new scientific and technical knowledge, as well as professional competences to create scientific basis for the development and design of innovative product, process, and system. The acquisition of pedagogical competences is also important for graduates of PhD programmes. The FFCD Standards v1 focus the attention of the PhD programme designers on integrated curriculum with mutually supporting transdisciplinary courses, research and pedagogic activities with an explicit

plan of integration of personal and interpersonal skills, abilities to create scientific basis for innovative product, process, and system design and development using the methods of technological foresight (Standard 3 FFCD). The essential elements of the curriculum should be an introductory seminar that provides the framework for engineering practice in creation of scientific basis for innovative product, process, and system design and development (Standard 4 FFCD); research-design experiences (Standard 5 FFCD); teaching and learning based on active and research methods (Standard 8 FFCD).

3 Three-cycle of EE based on the CDIO-FCDI-FFCD triad

Table 1 shows the key roles of graduates of three cycles of EE at various stages of engineering activities (F₁ – Foresight, F₂ – Forecast, C – Conceive, D – Design, I – Implement, O - Operate). The table helps to better understand the system of division of labor between representatives of the engineering profession with higher education of various levels.

Table 1. Key roles of graduates of BEng, MSc and PhD programmes

Stage	Key roles of graduates of three cycles of engineering education		
	BEng	MSc	PhD
F ₁	Non-priority activity	Non-priority activity	Future studying; long-term visioning; analyzing the society needs; research & innovation planning; technological foresight; “critical” technology analyzing.
F ₂	Non-priority activity	Analyzing the market trends; making predictions of stakeholder needs; estimating risk and uncertainty; defining the most competitive innovative products, processes and systems.	Knowledge management; research and new knowledge generation; critical analyses of scientific data; assessing the needs of knowledge-intensive technology.
C	Defining customer needs for products, processes and systems; considering technology; developing enterprise strategy, and regulations; developing conceptual, technical, and business plans.	Feasibility studying, modeling and simulation; developing advanced technique and technology; assessment of the economic impact of innovations; planning and creating resources for innovation design and development.	Creating scientific basis for the development and design of innovative product, process, or system; developing new technique and technology based on up-to-date knowledge.
D	Creating the design, that is the plans, drawings, and algorithms that describe what will be implemented.	Designing & developing of innovative product, process, or system taking into consideration severe limitations.	Providing scientific support of knowledge-intensive innovative product, process, or system design and development.
I	Transformation of the design into the product, process, or system, including	Production management when implementing innovative project; controlling of	Non-priority activity

	manufacturing, coding, testing and validation.	advanced technology when manufacturing and coding.	
○	Using the implemented product, process, or system to deliver the intended value, including maintaining, evolving and retiring the system.	Non-priority activity	Non-priority activity

Table 1 indicates that for graduates of BEng, MSc and PhD programmes, activities at some stages are not a priority. However, this does not mean, for example, that Bachelors cannot participate in the engineering activity at “Foresight” and “Forecast” stages. If necessary, they should be able to do this under the guidance of Masters and PhD-holders, performing auxiliary functions. Also Masters should assist PhD-holders at “Foresight” stage and, in some cases, should lead Bachelors at “Operate” stage. In turn, PhD holders, if necessary, should also not shy away from activities at “Implement” and “Operate” stages, assisting Masters and Bachelors.

In practice, as a rule, engineering specialists with higher education of various levels work in a team (together with engineering technicians and technologists), performing various functions when creating technical products, processes and systems. At the same time, the highest productivity of labor is achieved if each specialist is engaged in its priority business at various stages and successfully fulfills its key roles indicated in Table 1. In order to prepare graduates of engineering BEng, MSc and PhD programmes to perform their functions with maximum efficiency, it is recommended to design three-cycle programmes on the basis of the CDIO-FCDI-FFCD triad.

4 Piloting the CDIO-FCDI-FFCD triad in Kuban State Technological University

Kuban State Technological University (KubSTU) is one of the largest research, educational and cultural centers in the South of Russia (<http://kubstu.ru/en>). The University trains engineers for high-tech industry and offers undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate programmes.

In 2017 the new version of the Russian Federal State Educational Standards (FSES 3++) was introduced (<http://fgosvo.ru/fgosvo/151/150/24>). In this regard, the University developed a strategic plan for the modernization of three-cycle engineering programmes. Engineering programmes leading to BEng, MSc and PhD degrees in food production technologies were selected as pilot programmes to be redesigned based on CDIO-FCDI-FFCD triad. Author of the paper was invited to lead the design process as KubSTU Rectorate Advisor.

First of all, the objectives and intended LOs of the BEng, MSc and PhD programmes were clarified based on KubSTU mission, FSES 3++ requirements, stakeholder needs and CDIO-FCDI-FFCD Syllabuses. Next, LOs of the three-cycle programmes providing graduates with competences required for activity at the five stages: “Foresight”,

“Forecast”, “Conceive”, “Design”, “Implement” and “Operate” were defined (Table 1). The diagram in the Fig. 1 illustrates orientation of the 4-year (240 credits) BEng programme LOs, 2-year (120 credits) MSc programme LOs and 4-year (240 credits) PhD programme LOs to F₁ - F₂ – C – D – I - O stages of engineering activity.

Fig. 1. Orientation of LOs of the three-cycle engineering programmes to F₁–F₂–C–D–I–O stages of engineering activity

The BEng, MSc and PhD engineering programmes were redesigned taking into account different orientation to complex, innovative and research engineering activities at various stages as shown in the diagram. The updated programmes have a modular structure.

The BSc programme consists of seven modules (Fig. 2): BEng1 – disciplinary module of social sciences & humanities, BEng2 – disciplinary module of natural sciences & mathematics, BEng3 – disciplinary module of basic engineering science, BEng4 – module of mandatory cross-disciplinary courses, BEng5 – module of variable cross-disciplinary courses, BEng 6 – module of internships & placements, BEng7 - module of final project & exam. The greatest contribution (ECTS credits) to the preparation of graduates for activity at the “Conceive” and “Design” stages is made by courses of natural sciences & mathematics (43 credits), followed by courses of social sciences & humanities (14 credits) and courses of basic engineering sciences (13 credits). The greatest contribution to the preparation of graduates for activity at the “Implement” and “Operate” stages is made by variable courses (57 credits), followed by internship & placement (20 credits). At the same time, each block of the integrated curriculum contributes to the preparation of BEng programme graduates for complex engineering activity at all stages.

Fig. 2. ECTS Credits (%) by BEng Modules

The MSc programme consists of six modules (Fig. 3): MSc1 – disciplinary module of fundamental sciences, MSc2 – disciplinary module of fundamental engineering, MSc3 – module of mandatory interdisciplinary courses, MSc4 – module of interdisciplinary variable courses, MSc5 - module of internships & research, MSc6 - module of final project (thesis) & exam. The greatest contribution to the preparation of graduates for activity at the “Forecast”, “Design” and “Implement” stages is made by internships & research (48 credits), followed by mandatory courses (17 credits). The contribution of fundamental science & engineering courses (22 credits) is very important to the preparation of graduates for activity at the “Conceive” and “Design” stages.

Fig. 3. ECTS Credits (%) by MSc Modules

The PhD programme consists of seven modules (Fig. 4): PhD1 – disciplinary module of fundamental sciences, PhD2 – disciplinary module of fundamental engineering sciences, PhD3 –module of mandatory transdisciplinary courses, PhD4 – module of variable transdisciplinary courses, PhD5 – module of pedagogic internship, PhD6 – module of research, PhD7 - module of final work (thesis). Research (199 credits) is dominant in the preparation of graduates for activity at all stages. However, all modules of

the PhD programme curriculum contribute to integrated learning experience of PhD students. The main idea of the programme is to prepare PhD students for careers in academic institutions, as well as industry research and development.

Fig. 4. ECTS Credits (%) by PhD Modules

CONCLUSION

The modernization of three-cycle engineering programmes in KubSTU based on the CDIO-FCDI-FFCD triad is the first experience of practical application of the FCDI Standards and FFCD Standards developed by analogy with CDIO Standards. The programmes including face-to-face and online teaching and learning materials are being prepared for implementation in the next academic year. The results of the implementation of the programmes redesigned as engineering “triad” will be discussed with SEFI and CDIO Worldwide Initiative community in the future.

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